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ABSTRACT

Introduction: Hypertension (HT) is a preventable but highly prevalent public health concern (Mills, Stefanescu, & He, 2020). Within the scope of family medicine, efforts to prevent HT and promote health are of critical importance (Brouwers et al., 2021). This study aimed to assess adult attitudes toward HT prevention and contribute to awareness-raising on this issue.

Materials and Methods: This descriptive, cross-sectional study was conducted with adults applying to Family Healthcare Centers. Data were gathered through face-to-face interviews using a structured questionnaire, which included socio-demographic questions, items related to HT prevention, and the Hypertension Prevention Attitude Scale (HPAS). The HPAS comprises five subscales: Prevention-Control (PC), Habits-Lifestyle (HL), Nutritional Attitudes (NA), Psychological Status-Physical Activity (PS-PA), and Knowledge of Disease and Risk (KDR). Higher scores reflect more favorable attitudes. Statistical analysis was performed with SPSS v23.0; $p < 0.05$ was accepted as significant.

Results: As of the interim analysis, data from 121 participants were analyzed. Of them, 54.5% were female, and the mean age was 39 ± 14 years (range: 18–79). Educational attainment of high school or above was observed in 83.5%. At least one chronic disease was reported by 24.8%, regular medication uses by 23.1%, and a family history of HT by 54.5%. While 69.4% correctly identified normal blood pressure (BP) values and 58.7% recognized HT symptoms, 19% of participants lacked awareness of HT risk factors, and 9% believed HT was untreatable. The mean HPAS total score was 109 ± 12 . Women scored significantly higher in NA ($p = 0.027$). Participants with income exceeding expenses had higher PS-PA scores compared to those with financial constraints ($p = 0.043$). Education level significantly impacted total HPAS ($p = 0.009$), KDR ($p = 0.028$), and PC ($p = 0.011$) scores. Chronic illness or presence of a healthcare professional in the family did not significantly affect HPAS scores. A family history of HT was associated only with higher NA scores ($p = 0.033$). Participants exercising fewer than three times weekly scored higher in NA than those exercising 3–5 times/week ($p = 0.012$). Ownership of a home BP monitor was associated with higher PS-PA scores ($p = 0.027$). Recent BP measurement within the past 3 months was linked to higher NA scores compared to earlier measurements ($p = 0.004$).

Conclusion: Family physicians play a crucial role in fostering preventive attitudes toward HT. Special focus should be placed on men and individuals with lower socioeconomic and educational levels. Importantly, routine blood pressure monitoring appears to positively influence preventive attitudes.

PEER REVIEW STATEMENT

This paper has undergone a double-blind peer review process and has been approved by the scientific committee of the conference.

KEYWORDS

Hypertension, prevention, family medicine, public health, patient attitudes

CONFLICT OF INTEREST DECLARATION

There is no commercial, financial, or personal conflict of interest in this study.

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